

Photocatalysis : a promising technology for wastewater treatment[†]

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Photocatalysis is a phenomenon, where an electron-hole pair is generated on exposing semiconducting materials to light of suitable energy. Thus, the chemical reactions that occur in the presence of a semiconductor and light are collectively termed as photocatalytic reactions. Photocatalytic reactions are mainly classified into two categories : (i) homogeneous photocatalysis, where substrate and photocatalyst both exist in the same phase and (ii) heterogeneous photocatalysis, in which substrate and photocatalyst exist in different phases. Different dyes and some soluble coordination compounds are used as homogeneous photocatalyst whereas different semiconducting powders are good examples of heterogeneous photocatalysts. This field has been extensively reviewed by various workers¹⁻⁹.

Exhaustive researches in the field of photocatalysis have shown various fascinating applications of photocatalytic reactions. In the present review, we are considering photocatalysis as a main tool in dealing with the worldwide problems of environmental pollution and wastewater treatment.

Inorganic contaminants

Photocatalytic conversion of OCN^- to CO_3^{2-} over TiO_2 was studied by Peral *et al.*¹⁰,

Pollema *et al.*¹¹ investigated photocatalytic oxidation of cyanide to nitrate over TiO_2 particles. In this photocatalytic oxidation, cyanide is first oxidized to cyanate, then photocatalytically oxidized via nitrite, all the way to nitrate,

This conversion is useful in pollution control since nitrate is less hazardous contaminants as compared to cyanide ions. Hidaka *et al.*¹² investigated the photocatalytic degradation of cyanide in aqueous TiO_2 suspension in aerated conditions. Formation of intermediate OCN^- and its ultimate mineralization to CO_2 and N_2 has been reported,

Industrial effluents, a major source causing pollution, are found to contain a number of metal ions which are toxic to aquatic life at higher levels. Although there are various techniques to remove these pollutants, photocatalytic treatment of such effluents may prove to be more beneficial than the other routine techniques.

Yoneyama *et al.*¹³ studied the photocatalytic reduction of dichromate ions using WO_3 powder in acidic range. Photocatalytic reduction of pollutant Hg^{II} ions on doped WO_3 suspension was investigated by Wang and Zhuang¹⁴. Heterogeneous photocatalytic oxidation of Mn^{II} over TiO_2 has been reported by Lozano *et al.*¹⁵ whereas photocatalytic reduction of the environmental pollutant Cr^{IV} over CdS powder was observed by Wang *et al.*¹⁶. Photocatalytic reduction of Hg^{II} and Cu^{II} ions in illuminated aqueous suspension of ZnO powder has also been reported^{17,18}. The faster Hg^{II} elimination under sunlight exposure suggested that this photocatalytic procedure might be used as a promising method for mercury depollution. Domenech and Munoz¹⁹ observed photoreduction of Cr^{VI} in sunlight using ZnO as an effective photocatalyst. Photocatalytic reduction of Ni^{II} over iron(III) oxide has been reported by Verma *et al.*²⁰ while photocatalytic degradation of Mn^{VII} over stannic oxide powder was observed by Ameta *et al.*²¹.

The photocatalytic reduction of the pollutant Hg^{II} salts using TiO_2 photocatalyst (Hombikat UV100) was also

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studied by Khalil *et al.*²². The photoreduction of mercury salts was studied as a function of irradiation time, pH of the suspension, initial Hg^{II} concentration and mass of the semiconductor in the suspension. The activity of Hombikat UV100 was compared with the catalytic activity of the traditional TiO₂ photocatalyst (Degussa P25). The reduction was found to be first order in [Hg^{II}]. Chen and Ray²³ removed some toxic metal ions from wastewater by photocatalysis. Photocatalytic degradation of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} over ZnO was reported by Dangi *et al.*^{24,25}. The following mechanism has been proposed :

Organic contaminants

Photodegradation of dichloromethane, tetrachloroethylene and 1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane in aqueous suspension of TiO₂ with natural, concentrated and simulated sunlight was investigated by Halmann *et al.*²⁶. Martin *et al.*²⁷ carried out photocatalytic decomposition of chloroform in fully irradiated photoreactor using TiO₂ particulate suspensions. Nishida *et al.*²⁸ studied photocatalytic degradation of trichloroethylene in the gas phase using TiO₂ pellets. Chloral hydrate, a toxic compound, is used for the synthesis of insecticides. Tanaka *et al.*²⁹ reported the photocatalytic degradation of chloral hydrate in aqueous semiconductor suspension involving •OH radicals as oxidizing species,

The photocatalytic degradation of CHCl₃, CHBr₃, CCl₄ and CCl₃COO⁻ was investigated by Choi and Hoffmann³⁰ in aqueous TiO₂ suspensions. A common intermediate, the trihalomethyl radical, is involved in the degradation of each substrate except for CCl₃COO⁻. In the absence of dissolved oxygen, CHCl₃ and CHBr₃ are degraded into carbon monoxide and halide ions, while in the presence of oxygen, CHCl₃ degrades into CO₂ and halide ion,

Soni *et al.*³¹ used zinc oxide as a photocatalyst for mineralization of carbon tetrachloride. They also observed the effectiveness of sensitizer on photocatalytic activity of ZnO and the order was : K₄[Fe(CN)₆] > methylene blue > crystal violet > unsensitized.

Pal and Sharon³² reported photodegradation of polyaromatic hydrocarbons over thin film of TiO₂ nanoparticles. Hennezel *et al.*³³ observed gas phase photocatalytic degradation of benzene and toluene over H₂O and HCl pretreated TiO₂. Photodegradation of fluorinated aromatics over titania in aqueous media was observed by Minero *et al.*³⁴. Matthews³⁵ reported photooxidation of organic impurities in water using TiO₂ thin films. The rate of photocatalytic oxidation of aromatic compounds obeyed approximately first order kinetics with the rate constants decreasing with increasing solute concentration. Photocatalytic and oxidative degradation of wastewater pollutants (some polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons) involving TiO₂ was observed by Das *et al.*³⁶. Recently, decomposition of toluene using TiO₂ catalytic system was reported by Kang *et al.*³⁷.

Photocatalytic degradation of biphenyl and chlorobiphenyls in the presence of TiO₂ was observed by Carey *et al.*³⁸. Tahiri *et al.*³⁹ demonstrated the photocatalytic degradation of chlorobenzoic acid (CBA) isomers in aqueous suspensions of neat and modified titania. The three pollutants disappeared from water in the order, 3-CBA < 2-CBA < 4-CBA. It was observed that the doping of titania with Cr^{III} ions or 1 wt% Pt deposited on titania was detrimental for the photocatalytic activity,

Uchida *et al.*⁴⁰ carried out photocatalytic decomposition of trichlorobenzene using TiO₂ supported on nickel poly(tetrafluoroethylene) composite plate. TiO₂/CdS catalyst was found to be more photocatalytic active than TiO₂ for photocatalytic degradation of 4-chlorophenol in water⁴¹. The photochemical degradation of *p*-dichlorobenzene on titanium dioxide in presence of Fenton's reagent was observed by Mogra *et al.*⁴²,

Heterogeneous photocatalytic decomposition of phenol over TiO₂ powder was studied by Okamoto *et al.*⁴³. The products at the initial stage of the reaction were hydroquinone, pyrocatechol, 1,2,4-benzenetriol, pyrogallol and 2-hydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone. These intermediates underwent further photocatalytic oxidation via acids and / or aldehydes finally into CO₂ and H₂O (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The variation in the activation energy for the initial stage of TiO₂ sensitized photomineralization of 4-chlorophenol was investigated by Mills and Davies⁴⁴ as a function of pO₂ and 4-chlorophenol. D'Oliveira *et al.*⁴⁵ reported the photodegradation of dichlorophenol and trichlorophenol in TiO₂ aqueous suspensions. The aromatic intermediate corresponded to the hydroxylation of the aromatic nucleus with the following order of reactivity : *para* > *ortho* >> *meta*. The release of chloride ions and evolution of CO₂ also follow pseudo-first order kinetics. Photocatalytic degradation of 4-nitrophenol in aqueous suspension was reported by San *et al.*⁴⁶. 1,2-dihydroxy-4-nitrocyclohexadienyl radical has been identified as the most probable primary intermediate, which then forms 4-nitrocatechol.

Sclafani *et al.*⁴⁷ studied photocatalytic degradation of phenol in aqueous polycrystalline TiO₂ dispersion. The influence of Fe^{III}, Fe^{II} and Ag^I ions on this reaction was also observed. These ions react readily with peroxo species produced on the catalyst surface and/or in the solution,

Experimental conditions for the continuous photoproduction of Fentons reagent (Fe²⁺ + H₂O₂) are achieved in this way. It is well known that monochlorophenols are moderately toxic to aquatic life and induce disagreeable taste and odour to water. These are ranked high among pollutants in the

environment. Photodegradation of 4-chlorophenol in water (sensitized by semiconductor) was reported by Al-Sayyed *et al.*⁴⁸,

Agugugliaro *et al.*⁴⁹ reported photocatalytic degradation of nitrophenol in aqueous titanium dioxide dispersion. Mills and Morris⁵⁰ reported photomineralization of 4-chlorophenol sensitized by TiO₂. Mills and Wang⁵¹ reported the oxidative mineralization of 4-chlorophenol by oxygen, sensitized by a thin film of TiO₂ (Degussa P25). Using a thin film, the process goes through the same mechanism as in TiO₂ dispersion and generates the same intermediates, 4-chlorocatechol and hydroquinone,

The kinetics of photomineralization show clear difference between a TiO₂ film and dispersion. Kinetic studies on UV photodegradation of some chlorophenols using TiO₂ catalyst was reported by Hugul *et al.*⁵².

Dillert *et al.*⁵³ studied the photocatalytic degradation of 2,4,6-trinitrotoluene (TNT) and 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene (TNB) in irradiated homogeneous solutions and in TiO₂ suspensions by varying concentration of hydrogen peroxide and the pH. In TiO₂ suspensions, the degradation rate of TNT was enhanced significantly compared to the homogeneous solution at all pH values investigated. The addition of hydrogen peroxide to the suspensions resulted in decreasing reaction rates almost over entire pH region studied. Under the experimental conditions investigated, TNB is degraded significantly slower than TNT in all cases. Maillarddupuy *et al.*⁵⁴ carried out degradation of nitrobenzene in water using TiO₂ as a photocatalyst. Devi and Krishnaiah⁵⁵ reported photocatalytic degradation of *p*-aminoazobenzene and *p*-hydroxyazobenzene using various heat-treated TiO₂ as the photocatalyst.

Photocatalytic degradation of sulfonated aromatics in aqueous TiO₂ suspension was observed by Sangchakr *et al.*⁵⁶. Obee and Satyapa⁵⁷ determined the intrinsic rates for the photocatalytic decomposition of gas phase DMMP (dimethylmethyl phosphonate) on TiO₂ coated glass substrate at room temperature. The products detected were CO₂, CO, methanol, methyl formate, methyl phosphoric acid and phosphate. The washing of deactivated catalyst with water was done for complete regeneration of the catalyst.

Dyes as a pollutant

In spite of many uses, the dyes are toxic and carcinogenic in nature and environmental contamination by these toxic chemicals is emerging as a serious global problem. Coloured solutions containing dyes from industrial effluents of dyeing, printing and textile industries may cause skin cancer (due to photosensitization and photodynamic damage). Secondly, dye containing coloured water is of almost no use. If this colour is bleached to give colourless water, then it is less toxic and in some cases, it is almost harmless. Further, this water may be used for washing, cooling, irrigation and cleaning purposes.

The photocatalytic degradation of crystal violet over semiconductor zinc oxide powder suspended in aqueous solution was reported by Rao *et al.*⁵⁸. Further, they observed that the rate of photocatalytic degradation of crystal violet in various semiconductors follows the order: CdS > ZnO > Fe₂O₃ > WO₃. Similarly, photocatalytic bleaching of xylydine ponceau and orange-G on semiconducting zinc oxide powder was reported by Sharma *et al.*^{59,60}. TiO₂ assisted photodegradation of squarylium cyanine dye under visible light irradiation was studied by Wu *et al.*⁶¹. In this case, dye is excited and then it injects an e⁻ to the conduction band of TiO₂, where it is scavenged by preadsorbed oxygen to form active oxygen radicals, which drive the photodegradation. TiO₂ plays the significant role of an electron carrier leading to separation of injected electrons and cationic dye radicals.

Nogueira and Jardim⁶² and Lakshmi *et al.*⁶³ investigated photodegradation of methylene blue using solar light and TiO₂ as semiconductor. Liu *et al.*⁶⁴ observed the mechanism of photooxidation of alizarin red in TiO₂ dispersions under visible light. Fabiyi and Skelton⁶⁵ carried out photocatalytic mineralization of methylene blue using buoyant TiO₂ coated polystyrene beads. Wu *et al.*⁶⁶ gave the evidence for H₂O₂ generation during the TiO₂ assisted photodegradation of dyes in aqueous dispersions under visible light illumination. Effective capture of the conduction band electrons at semiconductor microelectrodes led to the reduction of oxazine and thiazine dyes. Peral and Mills⁶⁷ studied the kinetics of photoreduction of methyl orange by ascorbic acid sensitized by colloidal CdS. Mills *et al.*⁶⁸ used EDTA as an electron donor for the photoreduction of methyl orange sensitized by CdS. Effects of surface charge on the rate of photocatalytic reduction of methyl orange and crystal violet were studied by Zang *et al.*⁶⁹.

Ma and Yao⁷⁰ demonstrated the photodegradation of rhodamine-B (RB) over TiO₂ thin films. RB molecules are known to react with TiO₂ after excitation by visible light⁷¹,

Kim and Yoon⁷² used TiO₂/Y-zeolite as a photocatalyst for photoreduction of methyl orange in aqueous medium. Wilke and Breuer⁷³ studied the influence of transition metal ions (Cr^{III} and Mo^V) doping on the physical and photocatalytic properties of titania. They observed photodegradation of rhodamine-B using doped and undoped TiO₂. New trapping sites are introduced by incorporation of transition metal ions, which reduces the lifetime of the charge carriers.

Xie *et al.*⁷⁴ observed photoassisted degradation of dyes in the presence of Fe^{III} and H₂O₂ under visible light. Ramazol red was degraded in presence of ZnO photocatalyst by Sivakumar *et al.*⁷⁵, while Neppolian *et al.*^{76,77} reported photodegradation of some textile dyes over ZnO. ZnO was used in the slurry and thin film form for photocatalytic degradation of acid green-16⁷⁸. Dyes and pigments consist of the single largest group of industrial chemicals produced within the overall category of dyestuff. Azo dyes constitute a significant portion. Nasr *et al.*⁷⁹ reported photocatalytic reduction of azo dyes like naphthol blue black and disperse blue-79. A photosensitization approach for the degradation of a textile azo dye, acid orange-7 was made by Vinodgopal *et al.*⁸⁰. They also used coupled SnO₂/TiO₂ system for photocatalytic degradation of a textile azo dye⁸¹. Hepel and Luo⁸² used nanocrystalline WO₃ for photoelectrochemical mineralization of textile diazo dye pollutants.

Efforts have been made to find out some suitable modifications to enhance the rate of photocatalytic degradation of dyes. Photocatalytic degradation of basic blue-24, bromopyrogallol red and orange-G over ZnO in presence of surfactants was observed by Ameta *et al.*⁸³⁻⁸⁵. On the basis of experimental observations, a common tentative mechanism for photocatalytic bleaching of dyes has been proposed:

Decolourization of textile industry wastewater by the photocatalytic degradation process was reported by Hachem *et al.*⁸⁶. All the dye solutions underwent decolourization.

The kinetics of the reaction were found to be zero or first order with respect to the dyes. Semiconductor mediated photocatalyzed degradation of an anthraquinone dye, remazole brilliant blue-R under sunlight and artificial light source was reported by Saqhib and Munner⁸⁷. Solar/UV induced photocatalytic degradation of commercial textile dyes with different structures was investigated using TiO₂ (Degussa P25)⁸⁸. The experimental results indicate that TiO₂ (Degussa P25) is the best catalyst in comparison to commercial photocatalyst, such as TiO₂, ZnO, ZrO₂, WO₃ and CdS. Heterogeneous photocatalytic treatment of simulated dyehouse effluents using novel TiO₂ catalyst was reported by Arslan *et al.*^{89,90}. Alaton and Balcioglu⁹¹ observed photochemical and heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of waste vinylsulfone dyes (reactive black-S).

Surfactants as pollutant

The extensive use of surfactants has created a new problem in environmental pollution because these are either slowly biodegraded or do not biodegrade at all. Further, the cationic surfactants undergo much slower biodegradation due to their bactericidal nature and are relatively more toxic as compared to other surfactants as far as plants and animals are concerned⁹². Many surfactants that are widely used cause severe problems for natural aquatic environment⁹³. Biodegradation of surfactant is a very slow and inefficient process⁹⁴. Some studies on photocatalytic degradation of cationic surfactants were made by Hidaka *et al.*⁹⁵⁻⁹⁹. Heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of the cationic surfactant dodecylpyridinium chloride was observed by Avranas *et al.*¹⁰⁰. Photocatalytic degradation of some surfactants like cetylpyridinium chloride¹⁰¹, sodium lauryl sulfate¹⁰² and dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide¹⁰³ over titanium dioxide has been reported.

Cetylpyridinium chloride

Similarly,

Sodium laryul sulfate

Dodecyltrimethyl

ammonium

bromide

The presence of water and oxygen is essential along with photocatalyst and light for their rapid photocatalytic degradation. Hidaka¹⁰⁴ investigated the photodegradation of surfactants with TiO₂ semiconductors from wastewater treatment point of view. Lea and Adesina¹⁰⁵ reported the photooxidative degradation of sodium dodecylsulfate in aerated aqueous TiO₂ suspension,

From these reactions, it is evident that a high O₂ : organosulfate molar ratio is required for complete mineralization of this surfactant to CO₂ and H₂O. Rao and Dube¹⁰⁶ observed photocatalytic degradation of mixed surfactants and commercial soap detergent products using suspended TiO₂ catalysts. Hidaka *et al.*¹⁰⁷ reported formation of ammonium and nitrate ions from photocatalyzed mineralization of nitrogen containing cationic, nonionic and amphoteric surfactants.

Pesticides as pollutant

Many chemicals like fungicides, herbicides, insecticides, disinfectants, antimicrobiols and nematocides are difficult to biodegrade through bacteria. Therefore, these toxic chemicals accumulate in nature and persist there for a longer span of time. However, it is possible to degrade them photocatalytically.

Percherancier *et al.*¹⁰⁸ investigated the kinetics of photodegradation of pesticide, carbetamide, in water suspension of TiO₂. The two pathways of oxidation of carbetamide were observed : (i) oxidation by $\cdot OH$ radicals, originating on the surface of the photocatalyst and (ii) direct oxidation by holes, created by the action of light on the semiconductor. Doong and Chang¹⁰⁹ studied the photocatalytic degradation of parathion using UV-radiation in combination with H₂O₂ and TiO₂ or iron compounds. The addition of oxyanion oxidant can enhance the degradation rate of parathion in the order : ClO₂⁻ > IO₃⁻ > BrO₃⁻ > ClO₃⁻. Oxalate and 4-nitrophenol were found to be the major intermediates in this degradation. The sensitized photocatalytic oxidation of the herbicide, terbutryne using tris(bipyridyl)ruthenium complex as a sensitizer and TiO₂ as a semiconductor was investigated by Lobedank *et al.*¹¹⁰,

The conduction band electron reduces dissolved oxygen to form hydrogen peroxide, which is followed by the generation

of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals¹¹¹. Then these $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals rapidly attack organic compounds. Tanaka *et al.*¹¹² observed photocatalytic degradation of 3,4-xylyl-*N*-methylcarbamate and other carbamate pesticides in aqueous TiO_2 suspension. Photocatalysis has also been used for degradation of pesticides like atrazine¹¹³ and as a bactericide for spectrococci¹¹⁴, while Nehara *et al.*¹¹⁵ made use of irradiated titania semiconductor photocatalyst slurries in aqueous media for photooxidative degradation of the pesticide permethrin. Muszkat *et al.*¹¹⁶ reported solar photocatalyzed degradation of pesticides in rinse waters of agricultural sprayers and in heavily polluted well-water. Recently, semiconductor mediated photocatalyzed degradation of two selected pesticide derivatives, terbacil and 2,4,5-tribromoimidazole in aqueous suspension has been reported by Munner *et al.*¹¹⁷. Topalov¹¹⁸ reported the photocatalytic oxidation of the herbicide (4-chloro-2-methylphenoxy)acetic acid over TiO_2 while Kerzhentser *et al.*¹¹⁹ observed total degradation of the insecticide fenitrothion under photocatalytic conditions at room temperature.

Miscellaneous pollutants

Suri *et al.*¹²⁰ reported heterogeneous photocatalytic oxidation of hazardous organic contaminants in water. Prairie *et al.*¹²¹ investigated TiO_2 assisted photocatalysis for the treatment of water contaminated with metals and organic chemicals. The photokilling of malignant cells with ultrafine TiO_2 powder was studied by Cai *et al.*¹²². They also observed an increment in photocatalytic killing of cancer cells using TiO_2 with the aid of superoxide dismutase¹²³. Muneer *et al.*¹²⁴ investigated the photocatalytic degradation of an industrial pollutant like methyl vinyl ketone in aqueous solution using suspended TiO_2 and TiO_2 immobilized on glass surface. The two oxidizing species $\bullet\text{OH}$ and $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$ are the primary species utilized in photocatalytic degradation process. These oxidation reactions resulted in the depletion of O_2 and methyl vinyl ketone and in the formation of CO_2 and other semioxidized products in solution,

Organic contaminants in water can be completely mineralized by irradiation in the presence of semiconductor, TiO_2 ¹²⁵⁻¹³⁰. Demineralization of organic pollutants on the dye-modified TiO_2 semiconductor particulate system using visible light was observed¹³¹. Herrmann¹³² reported application of heterogeneous photocatalysis in removing various types of aqueous pollutants. Muszkat¹³³ reported solar degradation of xenobiotic contaminants in polluted well-water. Adsorption properties of TiO_2 related to the photocatalytic degradation of organic contaminants in water were reported by Chen *et al.*¹³⁴.

Copper occurs in several industrial effluents, resulting in significant loss of metal as well as destruction of organisms exposed to the streams. Reiche *et al.*¹³⁵ reported the deposition of Cu from aqueous solutions in suspensions of TiO_2 and WO_3 under irradiation. Machado *et al.*¹³⁶ reported the photochemical bleaching of chemical pulps catalyzed by TiO_2 . Mansilla and Villasenov¹³⁷ investigated ZnO-catalyzed photodegradation of Kraft-black liquor, which is an effluent from pulp and paper industry. Platinum-impregnated ZnO yielded 100% discolorization after 60 min (190 kJ m^{-2}) of UV-radiations.

Dagan and Tomkiewicz¹³⁸ used TiO_2 aerogels for photocatalytic decomposition of aquatic environment. Recently, newer photocatalysts have been reported for water purification with visible light and this too, with applications of combinatorial chemistry in search of these photocatalysts¹³⁹. The photocatalytic removal of bacterial pollutants from drinking water was carried out by Dunlop *et al.*¹⁴⁰. Vamathevan *et al.*¹⁴¹ investigated photocatalytic oxidation of organics in water using pure and silver-modified titanium dioxide particles.

Although the field of photocatalysis has emerged as an avenue for solving a number of problems of energy crisis, global warming, treatment of industrial and domestic effluents, but it has many more dimensions to be explored in future. Looking to the present trends, the time is not far off, when this method will be well received as an alternative technology by the scientific community all over the world for wastewater treatment.

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